

Transmission Zeros in Rectangular Waveguide Filters: A Novel Approach for Generating the Source-to-Load Coupling

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Abstract — In this paper, a new inline configuration of rectangular waveguide filter is presented for source to load (S-L) coupling to generate transmission zeros (TZs). The S-L coupling in the inline configuration is realized by a waveguide section with small cross-section. In contrast to the folded structure, in an inline configuration input and output are distant as they are at the opposite side of the filter. This results in a long waveguide line connecting input and output that behaves as an overmoded cavity generating several spurious frequencies. In this paper, a method for the suppression of such resonances is presented. In order to demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed approach, a 4th order waveguide filter centered at 9.55 GHz having F.B.W of 3.2%, 2 TZs, and suppressed resonances generated by S-L coupling resonator is designed. Analysis of both equivalent circuit and EM simulation is presented.

Index Terms — Equivalent circuit, source to load (S-L) coupling, transmission zeros (TZs), waveguide cavity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern communication system demands stringent requirements in terms of filters selectivity, losses, and volume. Bandpass filters with high selectivity and high quality (Q) factor especially for satellite applications are required. Due to its low loss, high Q-factor and high-power handling capability, waveguide filters are still of much interest in satellite communication system [1].

Usually, higher order filters are adopted to get a response with better selectivity. However, this increases the overall volume of the system as well as losses. Another way to improve filter selectivity is to generate transmission zeros (TZs) at both lower and upper stopband regions. Different techniques have been used to design filters with TZs. A well-known method is to provide source to load (S-L) coupling in order to generate TZs [2], [3]. The use of trisections to realize filter response with TZs is presented in [4]. Recently, waveguide filter with folded configuration employing S-L and bypass cross coupling is introduced in [5]. Something similar has also been studied in substrate integrated waveguide (SIW) structures [6]. Of course, direct S-L coupling in folded configurations can be realized easily as input and output are very close and can be connected by a very short waveguide section (or aperture) that does not resonate. On the contrary, realizing S-L coupling in an inline configuration requires a long waveguide section that generate spurious resonances.

In this paper, a new S-L coupling structure in rectangular waveguide filters with the inline configuration is adopted to

generate TZs. A method for suppressing the resonances generated by S-L waveguide section is presented. This is based on the asymmetrization of the S-L coupling section. The filter generating the passband is composed of classical rectangular waveguide cavities. The S-L coupling section is instead realized by a waveguide section with a small cross-section (e.g., height $h = 3$ mm). Both capacitive and inductive couplings are exploited at the input and output of the waveguide section for suppressing the spurious frequencies. The procedure is illustrated first at the coupling matrix level and then is applied to a 4th order full wave filter in rectangular waveguide technology. Full wave electromagnetic (EM) simulations show the practical applicability of the proposed approach.

It is worth noting that, despite the use of waveguide section for connecting input and output has multiple (attenuated) resonances, such resonances are out of the filter band and does not contribute to the in-band losses. This means that the additional losses introduced by this waveguide section are extremely limited as they are related only to its behavior as a transmission line. This allows keeping the dimension (i.e., the height) of the waveguide section very small, so that it does not significantly contribute to the overall filter dimension.

II. STUDY OF EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT WITH SOURCE TO LOAD COUPLING RESONATOR

The proposed procedure is first analyzed in terms of the equivalent circuit (coupling matrix). The equivalent circuit consists of resonators R1, R2, R3, R4 representing the filter resonances, plus an additional resonator (R5) representing the waveguide section implementing the S-L coupling that resonates out of the filter band. Fig. 1 shows its response along with the normalized coupling values. Considering that all couplings in the filter are inductive/positive, no TZs are present (or better saying TZs are in the complex plane) in the filter response. The filter resonates at 10 GHz, while the S-L coupling resonator (R5) produce an undesired resonance at 13 GHz.

Fig. 2 shows instead how it is possible to obtain a response with TZs and how to attenuate the undesired spurious resonance generated by R5. TZs are obtained by a different sign in couplings M_{S5} and M_{5L} , while the spurious attenuation is obtained by a strong asymmetrization of the input and output couplings to R5 ($|M_{S5}| \gg |M_{5L}|$).

Fig. 1. Four-pole filter equivalent circuit response without TZs. Normalized coupling values are, $M_{S1} = 0.89$, $M_{12} = 0.6$, $M_{23} = 0.435$, $M_{S5} = 0.2$, $M_{5L} = 0.2$.

Fig. 2. Four-pole filter equivalent circuit response with TZs. Normalized coupling values are, $M_{S1} = 0.89$, $M_{12} = 0.6$, $M_{23} = 0.44$, $M_{S5} = -1$, $M_{5L} = 0.05$.

III. FILTER DESIGN WITH TZS

The study of the equivalent circuit for S-L coupling and resonance suppression discussed in Section II is applied here to the design of a 4th order filter.

A. Filter Design without TZs

Fig. 3a shows the structure of 4 pole rectangular waveguide filter of coupled resonators R1, R2, R3, R4 with the additional resonator (R5) coupled inductively at the input and output providing S-L coupling. The response of the filter is shown in Fig. 3b. The filter band is centered at 9.55 GHz with F.B.W of 3.2%.

It is worth noting that the waveguide section R5 in this case introduces several spurious resonances below and above the passband (at 8.93 GHz, 10.05 GHz, 11.3 GHz, and 12.6 GHz). In terms of the equivalent circuit, this results in a structure like that in Fig. 4, where multiple resonances of the waveguide section connecting source to the load are considered. In any case, the working principle of this equivalent circuit is the same of those shown in Section II and identical strategies can be considered for obtaining TZs and spurious frequencies attenuation.

Fig. 3. Four-pole filter. (a) 3D structure. (b) Filter response without TZs representing equivalent circuit of Fig. 1.

Fig. 4. Equivalent circuit of the full-wave 4th order filter considering multiple resonances of the waveguide section connecting source to load.

B. Filter Design with TZs

In order to generate the TZs, and to suppress the resonances generated by S-L coupling resonator R5, the filter design procedure must be that illustrated in Fig. 2, where coupling signs as well as coupling values to resonator R5 are different. The proposed filter design is shown in Fig. 5a, and the response is shown in Fig. 5b. As can be seen, the resonances generated by R5 are well suppressed up to -20dB. This has been obtained by asymmetrizing coupling values to R5 ($|M_{S5}| \gg |M_{5L}|$). The asymmetrization has been obtained by using a wide iris at the input of R5 and a narrow iris at the output of R5. Note that the very wide iris not only generate a large coupling, but it also generates a capacitive (negative) coupling. This means that it allows the change of the sign in the input coupling necessary for obtaining the TZs. Two birds with one stone. It is interesting to note that the mechanism

works despite the real equivalent circuit of the filter is the one in Fig. 4. Indeed, the effect of the coupling irises in terms of the coupling values is almost the same for all spurious resonant modes. This means that the effect of making the input iris very wide, change the sign and increases the value of all $M_{S5}^{(i)}$ couplings (with $i=1,2,3,4$). This results in the attenuation of all spurious frequencies.

Fig. 6 shows what happens when the size w_2 of the output iris (responsible for the M_{S5} value) changes. As can be seen, when w_2 decreases the suppression of spurious resonances increases as well as the distance of TZs from the filter band. In general, the higher the difference between $|M_{S5}|$ and $|M_{S4}|$, the better the suppression of the resonances. Fig. 7 shows the final four-pole filter response with the TZs.

Fig. 5. Four-pole filter. (a) 3D structure. Filter dimensions are: $w_1 = 24$ mm, $w_2 = 6$ mm, $l_1 = 2$ mm, $l_2 = 5$ mm, $l = 101$ mm, $h = 3$ mm. (b) Filter response with TZs representing equivalent circuit of Fig. 2.

Fig. 6. Effect of further asymmetrizing S-L coupling resonator R5 by decreasing size w_2 of the output iris.

Fig. 7. Final four-pole filter response with the TZs.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, a new configuration of rectangular waveguide filter with inline configuration having TZs below and above the passband is presented. S-L coupling is realized by using a waveguide section with small cross-section. Resonance generated by the S-L coupling section has been suppressed by asymmetrizing input and output irises to the waveguide section. The equivalent circuit analysis has been verified by EM simulations for 4th order filter thus demonstrating the feasibility of the proposed approach.

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